

Urban ReLeaf

Action Plans for Urban ReLeaf Pilots II

D4.3

Document Factsheet

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Short description	This deliverable presents the action plans for the second phase of Urban ReLeaf pilots. It outlines the specific strategies and methodologies to be employed in six cities – Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, Utrecht and Athens – to address their unique urban challenges through citizen engagement and data collection.
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Acronyms

AQ	Air Quality
DCC	Dundee City Council
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
FAQs	Frequently Asked Questions
LoRa	Long Range
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PANACEA	Platform for Air Quality Assessment and Control in Europe
PM	Particulate Matter
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TRH	Temperature, Relative Humidity

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Executive Summary

The second phase of the Urban ReLeaf pilots builds on prior citizen engagement initiatives to address key environmental challenges in six European cities: Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, Utrecht, and Athens. This report outlines detailed action plans for 2025, emphasizing citizen-powered data collection on urban heat stress, air pollution, greenspace perceptions, and tree mapping. By leveraging technologies, such as digital tools and wearable sensors, and participatory approaches, the Urban ReLeaf pilot cities will enhance local policy integration and climate resilience. Strengthening collaboration between residents, municipalities, and researchers, Urban ReLeaf aims to embed citizen-generated data into urban governance by driving evidence-based decision-making and inclusive green transitions across pilot cities.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background – the Urban ReLeaf project and city pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process. Athens is undergoing a greening transformation with a new, citizen-powered tree registry providing critical data for better management of greenspaces. Cascais engages citizens in sharing perceptions and thermal comfort levels while using greenspaces to validate the effectiveness of its parks. Meanwhile in Dundee, a city facing increasing grey infrastructure in deprived areas, actions to enhance the accessibility of greenspaces are co-developed with citizens and stakeholders. Mannheim has a heat action plan to safeguard its most vulnerable residents but has identified critical data gaps. Citizen observations of trees and thermal comfort, when integrated with official data streams, will aid the delivery of climate adaptation measures. Riga engages diverse audiences to address concerns about air pollution and greenspace usage, to ensure better informed policies. Finally, in Utrecht, data on temperature, humidity and heat stress, collected by and for citizens, will help them shape effective mitigation strategies to reduce the urban heat island effect.

1.2 Purpose of the Document

This document outlines the action plans for the second phase of the Urban ReLeaf pilots, building upon the experiences and insights gained from the initial stage. Following up on the detailed action plans outlined in Deliverable 4.1, which focused on the initial set of campaign activities launched by each city in 2024, this document highlights the pilot cities' plans for new campaign activities being introduced in 2025 while also providing information regarding updates or extensions of activities that began in 2024 (Figure 1). It introduces new innovative approaches as well as refined strategies to further address urban challenges in six participating cities—Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, Utrecht, and Athens—by deepening citizen engagement and enhancing data-driven urban solutions.

Figure 1. Overview of pilot cities' campaign themes by year initiated.

While the core themes of Urban ReLeaf remain focused on air quality (AQ), urban greenery, heat stress, and public perceptions of greenspaces, this phase introduces new activities for each city based on identified issues, needs, and prior learnings. The initiative seeks to continue to leverage innovative technologies and digital tools, which are summarized in Table 1, to bridge information gaps more effectively, expand community participation, and strengthen the role of citizen-generated data in shaping official policies. By refining data collection techniques and fostering stronger collaboration between residents and decision-makers, this phase aims to support more adaptive and inclusive urban planning processes.

Table 1: Overview of technologies and digital tools utilized across pilot cities' campaigns by year initiated.

Name	Description	Themes Supported	Used by (2024)	To be used by (2025)
Partimap	An open-source platform for creating and sharing web-based surveys	Greenspace Perceptions	Cascais, Dundee	Mannheim, Utrecht, Dundee
Urban ReLeaf Cities mobile application	IIASA-developed cross-platform mobile application to help deliver bespoke surveys to promote citizen engagement	Greenspace Perceptions	Dundee	Utrecht, Dundee
Participatory Tree Registry mobile application	CIBOS-developed custom city-specific mobile applications that allow participants to contribute information about their city's trees	Tree Registry	Mannheim	Athens, Mannheim

Name	Description	Themes Supported	Used by (2024)	To be used by (2025)
PurpleAir Air Pollution Monitors	PurpleAir PA-II (PurpleAir Inc, Draper UT, USA) sensor-based monitor measuring PM _{2.5} concentrations.	Air Quality	Riga, Athens	Dundee, Riga, Athens
TRH Wearable sensor and EcoPulse mobile app	Wearable sensors and an accompanying ICCS-developed mobile application to measure temperature and relative humidity, with an option for users to indicate their perception of hot and cold stress.	Heat Stress	Utrecht	Cascais, Riga, Dundee, Athens, Utrecht

The document provides a structured approach for implementing these action plans, emphasizing how each city can optimize citizen science efforts and leverage emerging technologies to advance urban greening and climate resilience. It highlights the necessity of sustained public involvement to ensure policies are grounded in lived experiences and local needs. Additionally, it reinforces the project's long-term goal of embedding citizen-driven insights into municipal governance, promoting data-informed policymaking and a more participatory approach to urban development.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The document is organized into key sections to provide a comprehensive overview of the action plans. Each of the six pilot cities—Athens, Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, and Utrecht—has a dedicated section that includes:

- **General 2025 Campaign Elements** – main aspects of the campaign including topic/theme, key goals or aims, the local significance/urgency, relevant policies to be informed, geographic or neighborhood focus, and technologies to be used.
- **Audience Engagement Plan** – description of targeted audiences identified, key partners, engagement history and importance, recruitment strategies, training/resources, and any potential barriers or anticipated challenges.
- **Data Collection Plan** – overview of the primary data to be collected, sampling strategies and collection methods, tools and technologies to be used, and relevant data-related considerations.
- **Campaign Timeline** – key activities and events for new campaigns launched in 2025 by month.
- **Conclusion or Continuation of Campaign Activities begun in 2024** – description of new, continued, or concluded activities related to the campaigns initiated by pilot cities in 2024.

This structured approach focuses on each pilot city's action plans for new themes and/or activities they are initiating in 2025 while also giving brief updates on continued efforts of campaigns launched previously. By largely focusing on details related to audience engagement and data collection/management, pilot cities will apply lessons learned during 2024 campaign activities to streamline efforts and minimize potential challenges or obstacles related to these domains.

2 Cascais

2.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Heat Stress Monitoring

Campaign activities for 2025 in Cascais will focus on engaging citizens in monitoring heat stress to better understand urban thermal comfort and its impact on public health. By identifying “hot spots” that require intervention and “comfort spots” that provide relief during extreme heat, the campaign seeks to create a citizen-driven thermal comfort map of Cascais. This initiative will inform policy and planning decisions, particularly in the context of the Cascais Climate Adaptation Plan and the municipality’s 2050 Carbon Neutrality Roadmap. The campaign is particularly urgent given the increasing health risks associated with extreme heat. The primary goal is to influence greenspace regulations, ensuring that urban parks and public areas are designed to provide better climate resilience and comfort for all residents.

The campaign will focus on key public spaces, including Penedo Urban Park, Quinta da Carreira Urban Park, Abóboda Urban Park, Fontainhas Woods, Trajouce Urban Park, Constantino Garden, and Cascais Centre. Temperature and relative humidity (TRH) sensors and the EcoPulse smartphone mobile application will be the primary data collection tools, allowing participants to document temperature as well as their thermal comfort perceptions at various locations based on real-time weather conditions. The application will also feature a visual map displaying collected assessments, helping city planners and policymakers make informed decisions. While the campaign targets the general public, special emphasis will be placed on vulnerable groups, including the elderly and students.

2.2 Audience Engagement Plan

The Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign in Cascais seeks to engage a diverse audience, including residents, tourists, elderly individuals, and students, to collect valuable thermal comfort perception data in urban parks. General audiences and visitors will be approached directly in the parks by young volunteers from *Cascais Jovem* (city youth volunteers program), with engagement incentives such as sustainable gifts for participants. The campaign will be supported by Cascais Ambiente's Greenspaces Department and the City of Cascais, ensuring that the collected data informs public policy and urban planning. Motivation for participation is driven by concerns for well-being, heat stress, and public health, as well as the opportunity to contribute to the improvement of greenspaces. A potential barrier may be participants not fully understanding the campaign’s purpose or the importance of their contributions. To address this, volunteers facilitating the campaign activities will provide clear guidance and support throughout the engagement process. The campaign’s success depends on maintaining sufficient volunteer numbers, which could be a challenge given recruitment limitations.

In addition to engaging members of the general public, the campaign places a special focus on engaging vulnerable groups, including elderly residents and school communities, through targeted outreach efforts. Elderly participants will be reached via small gatherings, local newspapers, television, and senior citizen organizations, with recruitment efforts emphasizing social motivations such as staying active and being part of a collective initiative. The school community, including teachers, students, and college pupils, will be engaged through partnerships with *CascaisEDU*, social media, and local influencers. Unlike other groups, no major barriers to engagement have been identified for students, making them a valuable target audience for sustained participation. However, across all groups, potential challenges such as low attendance and participant disinterest remain concerns. Solutions include strengthening social media outreach, increasing collaboration with community organizations, and ensuring clear communication about the campaign’s impact. Volunteers will provide on-site assistance

during data collection, helping participants navigate the process and ensuring that their contributions are meaningful.

2.3 Data Collection Plan

The Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign in Cascais will collect temperature and relative humidity data as well as individual heat stress and comfort moments to assess thermal and bioclimatic comfort in urban greenspaces during the summer months. The campaign aims to address current data gaps by supplementing existing meteorological station data, which includes temperature, humidity, wind direction, wind speed, and atmospheric pressure. The data collection process will involve participants following predefined routes in selected parks, stopping at strategic points to measure environmental conditions and assess their thermal comfort. Factors such as shade, wind, proximity to water, and vegetation type will be observed to evaluate their impact on comfort levels. After completing the data collection, participants will gather to share insights and suggest potential improvements to enhance the thermal comfort of public greenspaces. The campaign will take place from July to September, with data collection occurring twice a month during morning and afternoon sessions to capture variations in environmental conditions.

To ensure effective participation, attendees will receive hands-on training and demonstrations for how to operate the mobile sensors and understanding data protection measures. Data will be shared with the Cascais City Council's Greenspaces Department to support climate adaptation planning and enhance urban greenery to better withstand heat stress. Additionally, the collected information will be made publicly accessible via the Cascais Data platform on Power BI. Participant engagement will be maintained through regular updates on Cascais municipality's social networks and the Cascais Ambiente website. No major challenges have been identified at this stage, but ongoing monitoring of participation and data collection efficiency will be conducted to ensure the campaign meets its objectives.

2.4 Campaign Timeline

January	Winter campaign to collect data on the perception of thermal comfort in the 7 urban greenspaces under study (same methodology used in 2024).
February	
March	Test the mobile sensors in each of the 7 urban greenspaces
April	
May	
June	
July	15 th – Volunteer training Data collection events: 16 th – Penedo Urban Park 23 rd – Quinta da Carreira Urban Park
August	Data collection events: 6 th – Bosque das Fontainhas 20 th - Trajouce Urban Park 27 th - Abóboda Urban Park
September	Data collection events: 3 rd – Jardim Constantino 10 th – Cascais Centre
October	Dissemination activities about campaign findings and outcomes.
November	Dissemination activities about campaign findings and outcomes.
December	

2.5 Conclusion of 2024 Campaign

The Cascais city team completed a fourth round of data collection events in January 2025 focused on the Greenspace Perceptions surveys, a setup of which can be seen in Figure 2. These winter activities provided Cascais with a final set of responses to complement the full dataset spanning four seasons since the launch in April 2024. Across all campaign activities associated with the 2024 campaign on greenspace perceptions, Cascais received 1,500 survey responses from over 1,400 different participants. These surveys were facilitated by 70 volunteers across the seven urban parks where data collection activities were organized, with nearly 60% of individuals engaged identified as female.

Figure 2: Setup for the Cascais greenspace perceptions survey winter campaign event in January 2025.

3 Dundee

3.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Heat Stress

The city of Dundee's citizen-engaged Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign aims to collect hyper-local temperature and humidity (TRH) data to compare heat conditions in greenspaces versus grey urban areas. This data will play a crucial role in informing local development plans, open space strategies, and greenspace initiatives such as tree planting and pocket gardens. Portable TRH sensors will be distributed to trusted individuals, including municipal parking wardens, community groups near parks, and frequent park users such as dog walkers. By leveraging the daily routes of these participants, the campaign will generate valuable insights into urban heat stress patterns, supporting more effective climate adaptation and urban greening efforts.

Topic: Air Quality Monitoring

Deployment Plan for PurpleAir Air Quality Sensors Near Craigie Barns Primary School

Dundee City Council are considering deploying two PurpleAir air quality sensors near **Craigie Barns Primary School**, located on Forfar Road, Dundee. One sensor would be placed near the busy road to measure traffic-related pollutants, while the second would be positioned behind vegetation, such as bushes and trees, closer to the school building to assess the impact of planting on air quality. However, meetings are yet to be held to determine whether this is the optimal location for the sensors. The project aims to compare air quality readings between these two locations, while accounting for factors such as traffic volume, weather conditions, and time of day. We will also engage with the school to obtain necessary permissions and discuss potential integration into the school's educational activities.

3.2 Audience Engagement Plan

The audience engagement plan for the Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign focuses on recruiting both general and vulnerable participants, leveraging existing relationships with trusted community groups and Dundee City Council (DCC) team leaders. Initial engagement efforts have involved discussions with internal DCC teams to gauge interest in the sensors, ensuring that recruited participants are both motivated and reliable. The campaign will prioritize individuals from groups already involved in Dundee's Urban ReLeaf project activities, particularly those working in and around the city's greenspaces. Additionally, to identify and engage vulnerable communities, outreach will be conducted through organizations that support these populations, ensuring diverse representation in the data collection process. Participants will be motivated by the opportunity to contribute to citizen science and influence local council policies regarding climate resilience and greenspace planning.

A challenge may be ensuring participants remain actively engaged, as remembering to participate and complete data collection missions could be a barrier. Additionally, technical issues with the EcoPulse mobile application, such as inconsistencies and the automatic mission timeout when users are stationary for too long, may disrupt data collection. To address these concerns, the campaign will provide clear guidance and resources, including a user guide and frequently asked questions (FAQs) available both online and in print. Continued communication with participants will also be essential, allowing them to report issues and receive ongoing support throughout the duration of campaign activities.

3.3 Data Collection Plan

The data collection campaign for Urban Heat Stress in Dundee will gather temperature and relative humidity data alongside real-time comfort feedback to assess differences between grey spaces and greenspaces. By deploying 60 portable TRH sensors to municipal workers, such as parking attendants, community groups operating within or next to greenspaces and individuals such as dogwalkers that follow similar daily routes through Urban and park environments, the campaign will capture a broad range of environmental conditions across the city. Participants will carry the sensors as they move through their regular routes, with the ability to log moments of discomfort using the built-in button.

This approach allows for a detailed comparison of microclimates in urban environments, helping to identify how factors such as tree cover, green infrastructure, and built-up surfaces impact bioclimatic comfort. The collected data will supplement existing datasets and provide new insights into how people experience temperature and humidity variations across different areas.

To ensure effective participation, all sensor users will receive a short training session on device operation and data privacy considerations. Data will be shared with Dundee City Council's sustainability and planning teams to support future urban greening initiatives and inform climate resilience strategies. Findings will also be communicated to the participating community groups, empowering them to advocate for enhanced green infrastructure in their neighbourhoods. The campaign will run from late May through the summer months, with periodic data retrieval for analysis.

3.4 Campaign Timeline

January	
February	
March	Internal testing of TRH sensors; Early talks with groups that may be interested in participating.
April	Identification of community groups and individuals that will receive TRH sensors; Development of user guide and FAQs
May	TRH sensors to be distributed along with training on their use
June	Check ins with groups who are using the sensors
July	Check ins with groups who are using the sensors, evaluate whether any sensors need to be redeployed elsewhere; Evaluate data and data capture methods and make any necessary adjustments.
August	Check ins with groups who are using the sensors
September	Check ins with groups who are using the sensors; Stakeholder update meeting to feedback progress so far to stakeholders and participants.
October	
November	
December	

3.5 Continuation of Greenspace Perception Campaign Activities

In addition to the new campaign activities described above, the city of Dundee will continue efforts with their Greenspace Perceptions Campaign initiated during 2024. The 2024 campaign activities resulted in the collection of more than 1,250 data points provided by around 100 citizens at parks across the city as shown in the map in Figure 3. These outputs will be built upon through a series of dedicated, organized events aimed at engaging diverse audiences in exploring and enhancing urban greenspaces by completing web, app, or paper-based surveys. Beginning with the *Nature Detectives* event in January, families in Douglas explored their local park using the Urban ReLeaf mobile application, supported by partners such as the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds, iNaturalist, and the Wee Forest initiative. This hands-on experience aimed to not only familiarize participants with the application but also encourage them to contribute ideas for park improvements. Subsequent engagement included academic collaborations, such as the *Tour of Dundee SuDS* in February, where 4th-year Abertay University students visited various sustainable urban drainage sites, using the application to record public perceptions. Similarly, another February event involved approximately 250 first-year St. Andrews University students participating in a guided field trip through Douglas Community Park.

Expanding outreach to new communities, the campaign will introduce residents to the initiative through Scrap Antics' programs in Templeton Woods in March, helping them navigate the Urban ReLeaf mobile application and encouraging further participation across the city. A key milestone will be the *Urban ReLeaf Stakeholder Meeting* in late March, bringing together city planners, community groups, and project partners to reflect on progress and outline future goals. Additionally, a series of family-friendly events at Dawson Park and Lochee Park during April and May will provide further opportunities for public engagement.

Figure 3: Map of Dundee parks with the majority having greenspace perceptions surveys submitted by visitors.

4 Mannheim

4.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Greenspace Perception Monitoring

The city of Mannheim will introduce new campaign activities in 2025 focused on assessing residents' perceptions of public urban greenspaces with an emphasis on thermal comfort, particularly in response to climate and weather-related challenges. As one of the hottest cities in Germany, Mannheim faces significant issues related to summer heat, which impacts both vulnerable populations and the broader community. The campaign aims to ensure that public urban greenspaces provide suitable conditions for people to spend time outdoors, regardless of weather conditions. It aligns with several local climate adaptation policies, including the Concept 'Adaptation to climate change in Mannheim', the 1,000-Trees Program, and the Heat Action Plan.

The campaign will focus on key public spaces such as Willy-Brandt-Platz, Paradeplatz, and Friedrichsplatz. Web-based surveys using the Partimap platform will be used to collect data on citizen preferences and comfort levels in these areas with a series of survey questions related to urban square design with a focus on greenspace perceptions and thermal comfort. The campaign will particularly engage members of vulnerable groups, especially the elderly, to ensure their needs are considered in urban planning. By gathering data and engaging the public, the initiative aims to create cooler, more liveable public spaces that can better withstand extreme weather conditions.

4.2 Audience Engagement Plan

The campaign aims to make public spaces more comfortable and accessible, especially in the face of extreme heat. The audience engagement plan for the Mannheim campaign focuses on involving members of vulnerable groups, particularly elderly residents of Mannheim, to ensure their perspectives are incorporated into the design of public spaces. Engaging this audience is crucial, as these spaces should serve the needs of all residents, with special attention to those most affected by extreme climate conditions. To encourage participation, the campaign highlights the opportunity for citizens to actively contribute to making their neighborhoods more livable. However, potential barriers such as reluctance to take part in outreach interviews must be addressed through personalized, on-site engagement. The recruitment strategy emphasizes direct personal contact with visitors to the public spaces, ensuring that participants only need to answer questions, with their responses being fully documented by trained interviewers affiliated with contracted partner organizations. While no extensive participation effort is required from them, challenges such as initial hesitancy or lack of willingness to engage will need to be managed through clear communication.

4.3 Data Collection Plan

The data collection and management plan for the Mannheim campaign centres on gathering insights into how citizens perceive, and use selected public spaces, with a focus on comfort in varying climate conditions. Using Partimap to host the survey, the campaign will assess where people feel most comfortable – whether near water, in shaded areas, or exposed to sunlight – and explore the factors that influence their decision to stay in particular spaces or areas. This data will help validate or challenge the urban planning department's current assumptions about climate-adapted public spaces and inform future redesign efforts. Existing data sets from the Smart City Mannheim climate measurement network and the Mannheim city climate analysis will provide a baseline for analysis, while new data collected through the

campaign will enhance understanding of citizen preferences. Personal sociodemographic data, including gender, age, and education level, may also be collected.

Data will be gathered through outreach surveys conducted by contracted interviewers utilizing tablet devices in key public squares during the summer months (July and August), with a targeted approach focusing on vulnerable groups, particularly elderly individuals and, in some cases, homeless populations. Each location will be surveyed multiple times, and approximate geolocation data will be recorded within digital maps integrated into the Partimap survey to account for elements such as ground coverings, vegetation, and shaded areas. Additional environmental factors, including air temperature, solar radiation, wind, and humidity, may be measured using mobile or stationary sensors from Smart City Mannheim (SCM). Key challenges include the potential influence of existing infrastructure (e.g., benches, markets, or play areas) on responses, requiring careful documentation and clearly defined survey questions. The collected data will be integrated into relevant city planning initiatives and made accessible for further urban development projects.

4.4 Campaign Timeline

January	Announcement of the new campaign at the New Year's event
February	Coordination with internal and external stakeholders; Identification of data collection sites Drafting Partimap survey items
March	Drafting Partimap survey items
April	Find interviewers and develop survey
May	Technical/regulatory preparation of survey (e.g. contract with interviewers, terms and conditions for using Partimap); Preparation Heat Action Day
June	Last preparation of survey (e.g. test survey on Partimap); Heat Action Day (04 June)
July	Survey period
August	Survey period
September	
October	Data analysis and evaluation
November	Dissemination activities about campaign findings and outcomes
December	

4.5 Continuation of Tree Registry Campaign Activities

The Tree Registry Campaign in Mannheim will build upon its efforts initiated in 2024 aimed at expanding the city's knowledge of urban trees while raising public awareness about tree preservation, urban greening, and climate adaptation. These activities engaged almost 100 citizens and provided over 250 data points. As Mannheim continues to face increasing heat stress, expanding tree coverage is a crucial mitigation strategy. This campaign encourages citizens to actively contribute to a comprehensive tree registry by using an app to document trees, including their species, height, and location. The collected data will help municipal departments optimize tree management and identify potential areas for future plantings. While the campaign targets the entire city, particular attention is given to Feudenheim, a neighbourhood with an engaged civic society and an identified need for more tree-related data. The campaign aligns with existing climate policies, including the 1,000-Trees Program and the Heat Action Plan, reinforcing broader urban sustainability efforts.

To engage and recruit members of the general public, the campaign will promote participation through public events such as the New Year's reception, Heat Action Day, and the Greening Fair, as shown in Figure 4. Various outreach strategies will be employed, including targeted neighbourhood campaigns, collaborations with community groups, and engagement with local leaders. Challenges such as technology barriers, lack of smartphone access, and limited incentive for long-term engagement will be addressed through app improvements, motivational elements, and notification features. District walks and weekly market outreach in Feudenheim will also help foster community involvement, ensuring that data collection efforts are widely accessible and inclusive.

Data collection will be facilitated through the "Urban ReLeaf – Mannheims Bäume" app, available in both expert and public versions. Users can register trees at any time by documenting tree species, height, circumference, and condition. The collected data will be transferred to a secure server, verified, and informing the municipal tree registry. While participation is flexible, sub-campaigns will focus on neighbourhoods with significant data gaps, using events and promotional activities to drive engagement. The campaign will culminate in data analysis and evaluation in October, with further planning for sustained app use and continued tree monitoring in the future.

Figure 4: Outreach and recruitment event for Mannheim's tree registry campaign.

5 Riga

5.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Heat Stress

The 2025 campaign activities led by the city of Riga will focus on measuring urban heat stress with the aim of promoting awareness of urban heat islands and the role of greenspaces in mitigating their effects. The campaign seeks to educate the public on the importance of a "green lifestyle" while encouraging residents to consider greener and cleaner routes in their daily movement through the city. Additionally, the campaign will provide information about air quality (AQ) sensors and their role in monitoring urban environmental conditions. The initiative is particularly urgent given the high density of cars and associated vehicular infrastructure in Riga's city centre, which significantly reduces the availability of public greenspaces. As part of broader urban sustainability efforts, Riga is currently developing a greening plan set for completion in 2026 under the LifeLatEst Adapt project. Findings from related initiatives, including Life and Satisfaction, will also contribute valuable heat island data using satellite imagery, supporting the city's long-term climate adaptation strategies.

To engage the public, the campaign will focus on Riga's city centre, targeting residents and people working in the area. It will utilize TRH sensors and the EcoPulse mobile application to track environmental conditions, encouraging participants to interact with data collection tools as part of their daily routines. The campaign slogan, "Step closer to greener city), emphasizes a proactive approach to urban heat resilience. Public engagement strategies include informational displays at locations such as benches and dog parks, where residents can learn about urban greening initiatives and apply for related projects.

5.2 Audience Engagement Plan

The Heat Stress Campaign in Riga is designed to engage a diverse general audience through active and passive outreach efforts. The campaign aims to involve citizens that previously expressed interest in the AQ campaign, residents affiliated with neighbourhood associations, and dog owners/walkers. Additionally, around 20 sensors will be distributed to municipal workers including public park gardeners and parking/traffic enforcement, allowing for continuous data collection in key areas. Support of local non-governmental organisations (NGOs) such as Pilsēta cilvēkiem and Zaļā brīvība, which focus on sustainable urban development, will be relevant to meaningfully engage residents. Neighbourhood associations will help in sensor distribution, ensuring local activists, architects, and developers are involved in understanding and mitigating heat islands. A pre-existing list of interested citizens from the prior air quality sensor initiative provides a foundation for outreach, ensuring sustained participation.

To maintain engagement, participants will be encouraged to share their progress through a WhatsApp group that fosters community interaction and motivation. A gamification approach will add excitement, with categories such as "Forest Gump" (most kilometres walked), "Tropical King/Queen" (most data points collected in heatwaves), and "The Guardian" (most collection points per neighbourhood). Orientation challenges, where participants gather "puzzle" elements from different points of interest, will further encourage active participation. However, challenges such as lack of time, disinterest, or residents leaving the city in summer must be addressed through regular reminders and flexible participation strategies. A potential solution is sensor-sharing contracts between associations, ensuring data collection continues even if individuals become unavailable. The campaign will provide on-demand training and clear guidelines to participants, with consideration of whether a minimum activity level should be required to keep participants engaged and maintain high-quality data collection.

5.3 Data Collection Plan

The Heat Stress Campaign will collect temperature and relative humidity data to assess the heat island effect in Riga's urban environment. A key focus is addressing current data gaps by correlating air quality data with other environmental factors that influence urban air conditions. The campaign will build on existing datasets, including satellite data, the LifeLatEst Adapt project's layer comparing land surface temperatures between observation points and green areas, and a 2016 study analysing satellite images and 3D laser scans to map surface temperatures and land cover relationships. TRH sensors and the accompanying EcoPulse mobile app will be the primary data collection tools, strategically distributed to participants residing throughout the city to gather real-time environmental data. Ensuring data accessibility and utility, the collected information will support ongoing climate adaptation initiatives and provide actionable insights for urban planning. Anticipated challenges include maintaining participant engagement and ensuring high-quality data collection, which will be addressed through clear guidance, training, and ongoing communication with participants.

5.4 Campaign Timeline

January	Strategizing meetings with municipal partners and stakeholders about the data visualizations
February	Testing TRH sensors among project members; Meeting with data protection officer regarding campaign data and ethics considerations
March	Meeting with other municipal project teams gathering data relevant to heat island observations; Outreach to neighbourhood associations about participation in TRH campaign activities
April	Outreach to public park gardeners and parking/traffic enforcement; Development of the visual identity of the TRH campaign; First event dedicated to campaign in the end of April
May	Data collection activities begin; Educational activities (lecture)
June	Continuing data collection activities; Educational activities (city walk)
July	Continuing data collection activities; Educational activities (city walk)
August	Conclude data collection activities; Educational activities (city walk)
September	Conclude data collection activities / educational activities (lecture)
October	Host an event to share the campaign findings
November	
December	

5.5 Continuation of Air Quality Monitoring Campaign Activities

Riga city partners will continue with their efforts of the air quality monitoring campaign launched in 2024 by engaging a diverse range of audiences and stakeholders through educational initiatives and collaborative data utility and visualization efforts. The 2024 activities resulted in the collection of over 87,000 data points collected by the 20 installed sensors with real-time PM_{2.5} concentrations collected and shared on the PurpleAir map as shown in Figure 5. This year Riga aims to introduce educational outreach activities that will focus on delivering lectures and lessons on AQ monitoring and the health impacts of air pollution in kindergartens, schools, universities, NGOs, and youth centers, with the possibility of expanding to other interested groups. Riga will also be coordinating closely with the Smart City department to

explore synergies and potential support for how to best utilize the collected data. Additionally, workshops will be held focusing on the visualization of AQ sensor data, bringing together representatives and stakeholders from GeoRiga, Riga Digital Agency, and the Riga City Department of Housing and Environment to enhance data accessibility and interpretation. These workshops are intended to involve AQ sensor adopters and other residents interested in air pollution to share the findings of data analyses and present relevant data visualizations. Furthermore, input will be sought from sensor adopters to gather feedback on their experience with the PurpleAir map, identifying aspects they appreciate and areas that could be improved to enhance user experience and data usability.

Figure 5: Map of PM2.5 concentrations collected by Riga’s installed PurpleAir monitors.

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6 Utrecht

6.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Greenspace Perception Monitoring

The city of Utrecht will introduce new campaign activities focused on gathering local perceptions of urban heat and cool spots using the Urban ReLeaf Cities mobile application as well as the Partimap web-based surveys, with the goal of incorporating these observations into the Utrecht Digital Twin as a visualization and decision-support tool. The campaign aims to recruit participants from green-deprived neighborhoods, including Zuilen, Ondiep, Kanaleneiland, and Rivierenwijk. An emphasis will be placed on involving youth (ages 15-21), students, and migrant women to ensure a diverse representation of voices in shaping inclusive urban policies.

By collecting citizen input at key hot and cool spots identified from TRH data collected during 2024 heat stress monitoring campaign “Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt” (“Green Neighborhood, Cool Neighborhood”), the campaign seeks to raise awareness about heat stress and contribute to policy discussions on climate adaptation. The initiative aligns with local policies such as the Municipality of Utrecht’s Heat Action Plan and Waterproof030, as well as provincial programs on climate adaptation, urban biodiversity, and health and safety programs. Surveys will be conducted in key public spaces within the identified, green-deprived target neighborhoods. The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment is involved as an independent knowledge partner to investigate perceptions of climate change skepticism among residents.

6.2 Audience Engagement Plan

The 2025 campaign broadens its scope: in breadth’ it engages the existing general representative communities to consolidate the citizen science approach, in depth’ we strengthen the outreach to specific vulnerable groups within the neighbourhoods, particularly residents in green-deprived neighborhoods who are most affected by high temperatures. To overcome engagement barriers such as lack of interest in heat-related issues and difficulties using technology, the campaign will utilize accessible recruitment strategies, including trained volunteers actively promoting the survey to passersby. Promotion via QR codes, explanatory signs, and information about related projects like “Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt” will help guide participants through the process.

6.3 Data Collection Plan

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign will collect data on public perceptions of urban heat and cool spots, focusing on factors contributing to temperature variation in specific locations. Participants will be asked whether they find a place hot or comfortable and why, with options such as lack of trees, limited shade, or high traffic for heat perception and wind, water presence, or greenery for cooler perceptions. Additionally, participants will have the opportunity to express interest in future planning efforts for these areas. Addressing current data gaps, the campaign aims to generate highly localized heat stress and urban heat island maps to complement existing datasets. The data collection process will involve signs with QR codes to complete digital surveys through Partimap or the Urban ReLeaf Cities mobile application, potentially supplemented by in-person outreach through volunteers.

Personal data such as gender, age, and education level will be collected along with general location data of the survey site. The sampling strategy will prioritize engaging participants in public spaces through clear informational signs and boards, with volunteers and civil servants

actively encouraging participation. While no formal training is required, clear guidance will be provided to ensure usability. A feedback mechanism may be established to maintain engagement and improve practices. The collected data will be integrated into decision-making tools, including the Utrecht Digital Twin, to support urban planning and policy development. Anticipated challenges include potential reluctance to engage and technological barriers, which will be mitigated by using simple, accessible survey formats and combining digital tools with personal outreach.

6.4 Campaign Timeline

January	Session with policymakers to identify targeted data outputs
February	Session with ambassadors to identify key survey questions/items
March	Develop specific campaign plans including survey drafting; Additional in-depth 2024 data analysis; Testing TRH sensors
April	Testing and updating the survey Testing TRH sensors
May	Engagement of stakeholder groups.
June	Engagement of stakeholder groups; Start data collection by students
July	Data collection activities (TRH sensor measurements & perception campaign)
August	Data collection activities (TRH sensor measurements & perception campaign)
September	Data collection activities (TRH sensor measurements & perception campaign)
October	Data analysis
November	Host a wrap-up event with participants
December	Communicate results to colleagues and partners

6.5 Continuation of Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign Activities

The Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign initiated in 2024 will continue in 2025 with some modifications and additions, including the introduction of integrating a heat stress curriculum with youth and expanding participation in the “Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt” initiative. Building off the success of 2024 campaign activities that engaged more than 325 citizens and collected over 60,000 data points on temperature and relative humidity, the campaign aims to increase the number of TRH sensors to a total of 160. Participants will continue to use the TRH wearable sensors and EcoPulse mobile app to collect and view environmental data (as shown in Figure 6), including temperature, humidity, location, time, and perceptions of hot and cool spaces. The data will be incorporated into the Utrecht Digital Twin for visualization and decision-making support addressing existing data gaps and refining super-local heat stress and urban heat island maps. The campaign specifically targets youth (ages 15-21), students, and migrant women in green-deprived neighbourhoods such as Zuilen, Ondiep, Kanaleneiland, and Rivierenwijk. By engaging citizens in data collection, the project aims to raise awareness about heat stress, promote urban greening, and inform policies like Utrecht’s Heat Action Plan and Waterproof030 initiative.

Audience engagement will be coordinated by the local subcontractor NGO *Natuur en Milieu Federatie Utrecht (NMU)* and will build on previous community activities, such as façade

garden days and neighbourhood safaris, which were well received. However, prior recruitment efforts did not effectively reach some of the intended target groups, so the 2025 campaign will take a more tailored approach, utilizing ambassadors—enthusiastic participants from the 2024 cohort—to connect with diverse communities. Key engagement strategies include collaborating with neighbourhood coordinators, district advisors, and organizations like GLOBE to reach secondary school students. A bottom-up approach will be emphasized, with campaign elements co-created alongside 2024 participants to ensure relevance. Challenges such as technological barriers, time constraints, and a potential disconnect between campaign goals and participants' interests will be addressed through clear messaging, incentives like €40 vouchers, and community-driven outreach strategies. Participants will stay informed through WhatsApp groups, newsletters, and a dedicated helpdesk to maintain engagement and motivation. A structured measurement campaign, running from July to September, will also include workshops to engage participants and policymakers. The campaign will be continuously evaluated to optimize strategies for long-term impact on urban climate resilience.

Figure 6: Visualization of TRH data collected in Utrecht mapped in the EcoPulse mobile application.

7 Athens

7.1 General 2025 Campaign Elements

Topic: Urban Heat Stress

The Urban Heat Stress Monitoring Campaign in Athens aims to engage citizens in tracking temperature and humidity exposure using wearable TRH sensors and in reporting discomfort on temperature conditions. With extreme heatwaves becoming more frequent in the region, the campaign seeks to collect real-time data to better understand and mitigate urban heat stress. The targeted participants, which include municipal cleaning agency employees, tourist guides, and general citizens, will be equipped with Bluetooth and LoRa (or long range) network-enabled wearables connected to the EcoPulse mobile application. This technology will allow dynamic monitoring of temperature and humidity as individuals move through different parts of Athens, particularly in the city center. The data collected will contribute to broader climate adaptation and mitigation efforts, informing strategies such as the *Climate Adaptation and Mitigation Strategy*, the *Climate City Contract*, and the *100 Neutral Cities* initiative.

The campaign's approach involves distributing wearables to citizens who frequently navigate the city, ensuring comprehensive coverage of various urban environments. By engaging individuals who are regularly exposed to outdoor conditions, the initiative will provide valuable insights into the impact of heat stress in different areas. The collected data will support policy decisions aimed at making Athens more resilient to climate change, while also raising public awareness about the risks of extreme heat. The campaign design is intended to be accessible to a broad audience, with easy-to-use technology and a user-friendly app to visualize the collected data.

Topic: Urban Tree Registry

The Urban Tree Registry Campaign in Athens aims to engage citizens in mapping the city's street trees, creating a participatory tree registry to improve urban green management and maintenance. Currently, there is a digital mapping of Athens' trees, provided by a research activity, however municipal services are evaluating it as not accurate enough. Hence this initiative is essential for validating the information on trees' exact location, type, condition, etc. and for enhancing climate adaptation efforts. By involving residents in data collection, the campaign will contribute to policy strategies such as the *Climate Adaptation and Mitigation Strategy*, the *Climate City Contract*, and the *100 Neutral Cities* initiative. The project will utilize the Tree Registry mobile app customized for Athens by project partners CIBOS, enabling participants to document tree locations, species, and conditions. In parallel, the App is supported by a dashboard for trees management services that is aimed at being utilized by the relevant Agency of the Municipality, as well as, by employees in the city's 7 districts responsible for trees' maintenance.

The campaign will be launched in Kypseli neighborhood of the 6th municipal district by engaging school communities, equipping students in High and Junior High schools with mobile phones pre-installed with the mapping app. Students will take part in guided walks to map trees in their neighborhoods, incorporating gamification elements to make the process interactive and educational. As the initiative expands, more schools, university students, particularly from the Agricultural University, and other citizens will be invited to participate through online campaigns.

7.2 Audience Engagement Plans

Urban Heat Stress

To monitor heat stress exposure, the campaign will engage citizens in using wearable TRH sensors. Participants will include municipal cleaning agency workers, tourist guides, and residents who frequently navigate Athens' streets. Engagement efforts will involve distributing up to 120 low-cost TRH sensors and providing training on how to use them effectively. Alignment with key stakeholder organisations will ensure successful participation. Citizens will be encouraged to track and analyse temperature and humidity levels via the EcoPulse mobile application, contributing to a large-scale dataset that informs climate adaptation efforts while also stating through the sensor and the App their personal discomfort on specific temperature and humidity conditions. Feedback mechanisms, such as surveys and periodic evaluations, will be implemented to assess the campaign's effectiveness and participant engagement levels.

Urban Tree Registry

The tree registry campaign will actively involve citizens in mapping the urban tree landscape of Athens. The engagement strategy will be initiated in the Kypseli neighbourhood in the 6th municipal district, targeting high school and university students from the Agricultural University. Schools will be aligned with the campaign through direct coordination with principals, followed by small-scale training sessions and guided mapping activities. Gamification elements are being introduced in the mobile application developed by CIBOS to encourage participation, making tree mapping an interactive experience. The campaign will expand to additional districts, with further engagement events and educational outreach efforts. To ensure long-term involvement, assessments will be conducted through surveys to gauge citizen interest and measure the effectiveness of outreach strategies.

7.3 Data Collection Plans

Urban Heat Stress

The heat stress monitoring campaign will distribute up to 120 wearable TRH sensors to participants, who will use the Bluetooth and LoRa-enabled sensors connected to the EcoPulse app to collect real-time temperature and humidity data across the city. The TRH recorded observations aim to identify heat stress patterns and inform climate adaptation strategies. The data will be shared with policymakers to support urban cooling initiatives. Participant feedback will be gathered through surveys, and campaign results will be published on municipal platforms to ensure transparency and public engagement.

Urban Tree Registry

The tree registry campaign aims to digitally map urban trees in Athens, beginning with schools in the 6th municipal district before expanding to other areas. Students and other 6th district residents will participate in mapping tree locations, species, and health conditions using a web-based platform. Seasonal citizen observation campaigns will be conducted, with structured training sessions provided for participants. The collected data will contribute to a new urban tree inventory dataset, supporting biodiversity initiatives and urban greening policies. A series of structured events and school activities will be organized to maintain engagement, with evaluation surveys used to measure the effectiveness of outreach and data collection efforts.

7.4 Campaign Timeline

Urban Heat Stress

January	
February	
March	Coordination with key municipal partners and community stakeholders
April	Coordination with target audiences; sensor procurement and testing.
May	Coordination with target audiences; sensor procurement and testing.
June	Coordination with target audiences; sensor procurement and testing.
July	Deployment of TRH sensors and data collection in multiple urban locations, periodic analysis of heat stress patterns.
August	Deployment of TRH sensors and data collection in multiple urban locations, periodic analysis of heat stress patterns.
September	Deployment of TRH sensors and data collection in multiple urban locations, periodic analysis of heat stress patterns.
October	
November	
December	

Urban Tree Registry

January	
February	Release of updated Tree Registry mobile app
March	Release of the expert version for the Tree Registry mobile app
April	Testing of both updated and expert versions of the Tree Registry mobile app
May	Data collection activity with school in Kypseli
June	Data collection event with residents of Kypseli
July	
August	
September	Additional data collection activities with Kypseli school and residents
October	Additional data collection activities with Kypseli school and residents
November	Additional data collection activities with Kypseli school and residents
December	Additional data collection activities with Kypseli school and residents

7.5 Continuation of Air Quality Monitoring Campaign Activities

Athens will also continue activities related to air quality monitoring campaign focused on measuring pollutants such as PM_{2.5}. This year the campaign, which currently has 10 PurpleAir sensors installed and collecting data (an example of which is shown in Figure 7), has foreseen the installation of an additional 15 fixed-site sensors across Athens with 6 installed at nursery school buildings in March, 1 to be installed at a municipal building and 4 to be installed in public greenspaces. The collected data will be integrated into the PANACEA network (air-quality.gr), a data hub providing real-time air quality insights. This initiative supports the Climate Adaptation and Mitigation Strategy, the Climate City Contract, and the 100 Neutral Cities initiative by providing critical data to inform urban policies and public health measures. The campaign will introduce citizen engagement activities in 2026, such as workshops and public

dissemination of analyzed air quality data to raise awareness about pollution and its impact on health and the environment.

Figure 7: PurpleAir monitor installed at Municipal Veterinarian Center in Athens' 7th District.

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8 Conclusions

The second phase of the Urban ReLeaf pilots represents a critical step toward advancing citizen-driven environmental monitoring and urban resilience. Through the action plans for 2025, the six pilot cities—Cascais, Dundee, Mannheim, Riga, Utrecht, and Athens—are expanding their efforts to engage local communities in addressing pressing urban challenges such as air pollution, heat stress, and greenspace accessibility. These initiatives build upon the foundational work of the first phase, integrating lessons learned and refining strategies to enhance data collection, citizen participation, and policy impact. The incorporation of innovative technologies, including wearable sensors, participatory mobile applications, and digital mapping platforms, underscores the project's commitment to leveraging cutting-edge tools to democratize urban environmental monitoring. Furthermore, by fostering collaboration between municipal authorities, researchers, and residents, the pilots reinforce the importance of participatory governance in shaping sustainable and climate-resilient cities.

Looking ahead, the success of these action plans will be measured not only by the volume of data collected but also by environmental actions and urban planning and policy changes they inspire. Each city's campaign is designed to generate insights that inform long-term urban planning and climate adaptation strategies, ensuring that citizen-generated data becomes an integral part of official decision-making processes. Sustained engagement will be key to maximizing the impact of these efforts, necessitating ongoing outreach, capacity building, and knowledge-sharing among stakeholders. Moving forward, Urban ReLeaf intends to scale successful approaches, addressing emerging challenges, and strengthening cross-city collaboration to further amplify the collective impact. By continuing to refine methodologies and expand participation, the project aims to serve as a model for inclusive, data-driven urban transformation.

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